

D4.1 – Plan for the Dissemination and Exploitation of Results (DER)

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PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web	√
CO	Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement	
CI	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC.	

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1 Summary of the project

The development of "fault tolerant" quantum computation, unaffected by noise and decoherence, is one of the fundamental challenges in quantum technology. One of the approaches currently followed is the realization of "topologically protected" qubits which make use of quantum systems characterized by a degenerate ground state composed by collective composite particles, known as "non-Abelian anyons", able to encode and manipulate quantum information in a nonlocal manner. An example of such non-Abelian anyons are Majorana zero energy modes (MZMs), which have been reported in NbN/InSb/NbN hybrid junctions composed by a InSb semiconducting nanowire (characterized by large spin orbit coupling) proximised by NbN s-wave superconducting leads.

We propose two-dimensional oxides (2D-oxides) as an innovative technological platform for the realization of topological quantum systems. Our idea is to exploit the unique combination of unconventional **Rashba spin-orbit coupling (SOC)**, **2D-magnetism, superconductivity (SC)** and **high-mobility** in the 2D electron gas (2DEG) at the interface between oxide insulators, as for instance LaAlO₃ (LAO) and SrTiO₃ (STO). The basic element of this technology is a **quasi-one dimensional nano-channel**, whose properties can be locally tuned using electric field effect to create both topological and non-topological superconducting sections, and metallic or even insulating tunnelling barriers.

This platform has all the characteristics for the practical realization of theory-based proposals for topological quantum computation, and important fundamental and technological advantages. 2D-oxides technology allows a top-down approach for nanodevices realization, fully scalable to complex device layout including a large number of qubits. All the ingredients necessary for creating, manipulating and braiding MZMs can be realized using the same material and incorporated in the device layout in a seamless way. Moreover, **the strong sensitivity of oxide-2DEGs to the orbital splitting and occupation** of the non-degenerate 3d_{xy} and 3d_{xz,yz} bands, allows the development of conceptual new methods for the realization of a topological quantum electronics controlled by the orbital degrees of freedom.

Our project is aimed at establishing oxide 2DEGs as a viable platform for the realization of topological quantum computers, thus launching a new technological approach to the realization of "fault tolerant" quantum computation technology.

Our Consortium is composed by some of the most active and experienced groups working in the extended European Research Area (ERA) in the study of nanodevices based on the 2DEG formed at the LAO/STO interface, and comprises theoretical groups experts in topological quantum computation. The experimental and theoretical groups in QUANTOX cover all the research methods necessary to achieve the project objectives, which require the development and test of different typologies of quantum nano-devices based on oxides, to prove the formation of MZMs, and the design and test of quantum circuits which can demonstrate braiding on non-abelian anyons.

2 Executive summary

The main goal of the Dissemination and Exploitation of the Results Plan is to raise the awareness of the project activities both among the Academia and the wider public, in order to make QUANTOX a successful project with an important impact on Quantum Technologies.

QUANTOX project is committed to the implementation of a novel technological platform, based on the oxide nanotechnology, for topological quantum computation. The main idea is the engineering of topological quantum gates controlled by the orbital filling and splitting of the d-bands of oxide 2DEGs. Success in this endeavour will **set the early stage of scientific and technological developments of radically new, oxide-based, quantum electronics.**

2.1 Document maintenance

This document will be reviewed and updated as needed, as the project proceeds. This document contains a revision history log. When changes occur, the document's revision history log will reflect an updated version number, the date of the new version, the author making the change, and a summary of the changes.

2.2 Scope and objective of this deliverable

This document describes the Dissemination and Exploitation of the Results Plan of Quantox project. The purpose of this document is to determine all planned communication and dissemination actions during the project lifetime, to ensure an access for all interested stakeholders to public reports and to announce potential events where the project will be represented.

In more detail, **the objectives of the dissemination** are:

- To raise awareness about the project, its expected results and progress within defined target groups using effective communication means and tools;
- To exchange experience with projects and groups working in the quantum technologies field, in particular within the Quanterra Consortium and in close collaboration with the Quantum flagship coordinating activities, in order to join efforts, minimize duplication and maximize potential;
- To disseminate the fundamental knowledge, the methodologies and technologies developed during the project;
- To pave the way for a successful exploitation of the project outcomes.

The dissemination strategy and activities will follow **principles and best practices** as outlined in the CA Agreement section 8.2 and 8.3 in line with the EC Guidelines for successful dissemination.

The definition of the dissemination strategy is based on **the identification of the following milestones**:

- the subject of dissemination (what will be disseminated),
- the identification of target audience (who will most benefit from the project results and who would be interested in learning about the project findings),

- the definition of methods and tools (what is the most effective way to reach the target audience),
- the timing (when dissemination will take place),
- the dissemination management and policy (who is responsible of and how dissemination is ruled).

Following essential objectives of the project are identified:

- to communicate and disseminate the knowledge produced by the project
- to keep the contact at EC level with all relevant stakeholders
- to exploit the results of the project after its lifetime
- to provide recommendations for future developments

3 Section A: Dissemination plan

3.1 Subject of dissemination

The following general subjects of dissemination have been identified:

- Quantox project itself (general scope, coverage, goals and milestones and plans to reach them)
- interim results (reached objectives and achievements)
- techniques and methodologies (in respect of IPR issues)
- technologies (in respect of industrial IPR issues)
- innovation aspects (in an “open innovation” perspective)

3.2 Target audience

Four typologies of targeted audiences have been identified within the project:

- Research communities:
 - Condensed Matter Research Community
 - Quantum technology community
 - Quanterra Community
 - Quantum Flagship Community
- Industry:
 - Small and Medium Enterprises working in the field of quantum technologies
- Educational level:
 - Undergraduated, graduated, PhD students and young researchers to build the future quantum oxide community
- Regulating Authorities

Several dissemination activities will also be dedicated to the general public, as it will be described in the document.

In Table 1 we list the typology of dissemination actions and the relevant target audiences identified.

N°	Dissemination Actions	Targeted audiences
<i>Delivery the complex knowledge gained through the research at educational level</i>		
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantox website • Presentation and Video and Audio files for the most important seminars related to the activities • "News and views" commentaries and newspapers articles • Dedicated social networks accounts • Workshops, schools and open day events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SMEs and industries working in the field of quantum technologies • National funding agencies • Graduated and undergraduated students working in the field
<i>Delivery the complex knowledge gained through the research within the research community</i>		
2	<i>Delivery the complex knowledge gained within the reference research communities</i>	Condensed Matter research Community Quantum technology community Quanterra Community Quantum Flagship Community
3	<i>Delivery the complex knowledge gained within relevant SMEs and industries</i>	List of SMES and industries interested in the project activities
<i>Prepare the result exploitation</i>		
4	Prepare progressive deployment roadmaps for any of the results gained in the project	The grant agreement beneficiaries Future exploitation partners

Table 1: Dissemination actions and target audience

3.3 Dissemination activities

3.3.1 Internal dissemination

Our plan is to organize **two meetings/year among the partners** as well as frequent joint videoconferences to discuss recent results, advances, struggles, and on-going ideas. Moreover, we foresee strong exchange of researchers and students, with scheduled visiting periods in relation to the scientific and technological activities. An important outcome will be a creation of a network of young researchers, which will strengthen the international environment of the project and will allow young researchers, in the development of their future career, to interact with several research groups and with EU-SMEs and Industries (see External DER: Actions towards SMEs below).

3.3.2 External dissemination

Academic Actions

Project results will be shared with the scientific community through several communication

channels, scientific articles published on peer-review journals, participation in and organization of special sessions at the most important material science conferences (APS, MRS and EMRS, WOE). We will provide the maximum visibility of such results by opening our workshops and seminars to a very broad audience, which will include representatives of industrial entities potentially interested in our advances (see also communications activities). Publications in high impact factors journals will guarantee the permanent availability of the project outcomes for the scientific community. In order to assure adequate protection of knowledge of the project outcomes and of joint inventions (active policy included according to EU provisions), and at the same time capturing external interest, QUANTOX will provide **green open access to all publications that do not compromise the commercialization of results**, and **gold open access for the most important peer-reviewed manuscripts** published on high impact journals (IF>6) which provide open access. The dissemination of results will be also granted by the realization of a **project Database** with an open-access section. **The Data Management Plan (DMP), that will be delivered at month 5 of the project**, will define the type and the procedures to collect established data, reports, presentations, and developed codes. There are several data types according to the large number of activities foreseen within the project. The experimental data collected will be most generally in form of ASCII worksheets, matrices and images. Data acquired at synchrotron facility will be stored and treated according to the general policy of PSI-SLS. After their publications, the partners will provide open-access to processed-data files, generated using software like Origin and Igor, maximizing the expected impact of the most appealing outcomes. The project Database will be continuously maintained with at least one database storage external to the Consortium (like CINECA in Italy).

Actions towards SMEs and Industrial actors:

The exploitation of the project results will need, during and after the end of the project, dedicated actions that will be decided by the DCB after consulting representative of industries and SMEs potentially interested on the project, with whom the partner of Consortium are already in contact (like IBM, Hypres, Intel). In order to make the technology developed within QUANTOX to a pre-industrial readiness level (from TRL3 to TRL6), new projects with direct involvement of SMEs and large industries will be considered in the third year and after the end of the project.

Regulating Authorities:

For regulatory bodies, several dissemination actions are planned. Partners will promote results to policy makers and regulators in their own member states. A conference will be organized at the end of the project to bring the results directly to the attention of policy makers at EU level.

Communication activities:

Several activities are foreseen to enhance the communication of the project outcomes. Participation at major conferences will be a venue for announcing novel results and gaining the interest of potential investors. We will generate slides (in pdf format) and video/audio files for the most important seminars related to the activities of the project and distribute them to the widest possible audience. We will realize periodic newsletters and highlights to inform the highest possible number of potentially interested researchers, academic

institutions, SMEs and industries about the results and advancements of the project. Moreover, we will use all possible channels to make results public, like “news and views” commentaries, reports of the “large facilities” (ESRF, SLS), newspapers articles (in the respective countries). Moreover, QUANTOX will have dedicated accounts in the most popular social networks (Linkedin, Researchgate, Facebook, Twitter). It will also have a space in the Genova Science Festival (www.festivalscienza.it), one of the most relevant events for scientific communication in Italy and in Europe, and will participate to the European Researcher’s Night, a wide public event dedicated to popular science and fun learning. QUANTOX will organize two workshops on the project activities, open to the wider scientific community and to the SMEs and industrial companies interested in the 2D-oxides technology, open-day events for undergraduate students and PhD-schools in the field. The young researchers will be actively involved in the organization of all these events.

3.4 Management of dissemination and exploitation of the results

The plan for the dissemination and exploitation of the results (DER) will be managed by the Dissemination and Communication Board (**DCB**) composed by:

- Marco Salluzzo, the PI, marco.salluzzo@spin.cnr.it (General coordination)
- Barbara Cagnana, leader of WP4, barbara.cagnana@spin.cnr.it (IPR, Periodical reports, help-desk)
- Daniela Stornaiuolo, stornaiuolo@fisica.unina.it (Web, database, communication activities)

The DCB is in charge of collecting the information from all the partners concerning the activities and research results, collected to deliverables, worthy of dissemination and to propose to the PMB actions to make those activities and results public. Moreover, they will interrelate the dissemination and communication actions of each unit in order to distribute and promote to the target groups and to other stakeholders any information which can be made public according to policy defined in the sections 8.2, 8.3, 9.1 9.2, 9.3, 9.4, 9.5, 9.6 and 9.7 of the CA-Agreement. To facilitate the collection of papers, articles and presentations, so that these can be disseminated through the e-newsletter, website and social media, all partners are expected to provide this information periodically by sending a Publications/Dissemination Activities Form to the e-mail address created for the project: quantox@spin.cnr.it.

4 Dissemination tools

4.1 Visual Identity

One of the first dissemination tasks is the creation of a project logo. A good logo should be simple, in order to be remembered immediately, and, at the same time, able to visually convey the main idea of the project.

The QUANTOX logo is composed by three main elements: two spheres crossed by arrows and a blue “Q” letter intertwined with them. The two spheres represent two electrons with their spin. The spin arrows convey also the forward-looking vision of the project and the

concerted effort of all parties in achieving this vision. The blue “Q” letter represents not only the first letter of the project name, but also the coupling between electrons, hallmark of superconductivity.

We realized two versions of the logo: one with the QUANTOX acronym written in full between the two “spin” arrows, and the second, more compact, without.

The main colors of the logo (green, orange, blue and red) and the font used in it will be at the basis of the template which will be used for the creation of the project web site.

The logo will be distributed to all the partners to be used in their presentations, communications etc.

4.2 Website

The project’s website, currently under construction, is the main communication tool for the project. It will be hosted by the CNR-SPIN server at the following address:

www.quantox.spin.cnr.it

The design will be simple and clear; visitors will be able to reach quickly the information about the project and its main activities. We plan to make use of suitable photographs, sketches and charts in order to convey scientific information in a direct and clear way, also to those who are not involved in condensed matter physics.

In detail, the web site will collect all the key information on the project, such as the partners, the project’s objectives, its work packages. It will be also a repository for the project’s findings and results, where all the dissemination materials will be timely published, and for all the relevant news related to the project, such as open positions at the partners’ institutions.

There will be a page featuring links to other relevant projects carried out by the partners, a section for news and for events, workshop and conference, both organized by the QUANTOX community and related to the projects’ topics.

The website will become an important tool to ensure the project visibility, therefore a section

will be dedicated exclusively to interaction with the general public, with information presented in a clear, attractive way and material to be downloaded and used, for instance high school teachers.

A continuous exchange of information between the participants of the project is one of the most important conditions for the functioning of the QUANTOX network with its several international components. The website will also feature an interactive section, that will give access to the project main results and data (see also section Dissemination Activities – Academic Actions). Access to these documents can be made public, or it can be limited to certain users.

The web site will be updated permanently and it will be maintained for one year following the end of the project, in order to continue the dissemination of project results.

4.3 NewsLetters

The project newsletter will be issued periodically **every 6 months** as a part of the project website. It will provide relevant information about the progress of the project activities, results and events. It will contain the following sections:

- Project-related news (results, publications)
- Report on the progress of the project's ongoing activities
- Announcement of workshop and conferences related to the project's main themes
- Reports of project meetings
- Lectures, talks, and trainings opportunities

The eNewsletter will address mainly the academic sector. However, thanks to a simple and clear style, it will be suitable also to the larger public.

4.4 Dissemination Material

The project website will host a Download section where participants will be able to download files related to the project visual identity, as for instance:

- The logo
- Templates for documents and slides, featuring the QUANTOX logo and recalling its main colors (green, orange, blue and red) and font. The project participants will have the possibility to use these templates for scientific seminars, communication of results etc.
- A leaflet in pdf format, containing the project main information, such as summary and objectives and the participants' profiles.

4.5 Journalistic articles

Each partner will actively collaborate with the Communication Department of its Institution in order to communicate to the general public, via journalistic articles, the results obtained in the framework of the QUANTOX project.

4.6 Publication in scientific journals

The results obtained during the project will be made available to the scientific community through publications in high impact factor journals. This will guarantee the permanent availability of the project outcomes to the scientific community. News about publications and links to them (whenever possible) will be communicated via the project website as well as via the communication channels of each partners' institution.

4.7 Dissemination and communication plan

The dissemination and communication tools reported up to now are aimed at a composite audience: Academia, students, SMEs etc (see also section 3.2 Target Audience). The following Table (Table 2) summarizes the dissemination and communication tools with relative target audience.

tool	Target audience			
	Scientific community	Educational (Undergraduated, graduated, phd students)	Industry and SMEs	Public at large
Project website	✓	✓	✓	✓
newsletter	✓	✓	✓	✓
Dissemination material			✓	✓
Journalistic articles			✓	✓
Publications in scientific journals	✓	✓		

Table 2

5 Section B: exploitation of the results

5.1 Exploitation and management plan

The Exploitation plan is illustrated schematically in the Figure below (Fig. 1).

The PMB will collect all the Results obtained within the WPs and will evaluate these results for what concerns possible exploitation.

Industrial Pathway

If the results are potentially relevant for the Industry, the PMB will propose to the General Assembly a possible pathway towards the registration of a patent. In order to do so, the PMB will contact some of the leading Industries in the field of Quantum technology to have an expert evaluation of the potentialities. With the consensus of the General Assembly, following the principles established within the sections 8 and 9 of the CA-Agreement, the Parties involved in the results obtained will jointly deposit a patent. The Consortium will identify relevant potential stakeholders and will plan future actions in order to make the result relevant to industrial commercialization. Due to the nature of QUANTOX, we foresee, within the duration of the project, results with a readiness level TRL3. Thus the exploitation of the project results will need, after the end, dedicated actions that will be decided by the PMB

Fig.1 : Exploitation and management plan

and by the General Assembly in order to make the technology developed to a pre-industrial readiness level (from TRL3 to TRL6), like the realization of new projects with direct involvement of large industries.

Academic Pathway

The results which are not at the level to be of immediate impact for industrial application and patenting, will be managed by the Dissemination and Communication board. In order to ensure adequate protection of knowledge of the project outcomes and of joint inventions (active policy included according to EU provisions), and at the same time capturing external interest, QUANTOX will provide green open access to all publications that do not compromise the commercialization of results, and gold open access for the most important peer-reviewed manuscripts published on high impact journals (IF>6) which provide open access. The dissemination of results will be also granted by the realization of a project Database with an open-access section. All the actions described in section 4 of the DER will be undertaken timely in order to achieve the maximum scientific and societal impact.

5.2 IPR management

The management of IPR is strictly ruled by the Consortium Agreement (CA) which includes all provisions related, including ownership, protection and publication of knowledge, access rights to knowledge and pre-existing know-how as well as questions of confidentiality, liability and dispute settlement.

5.3 Exploitable results

The long term objective of Quantox project is to establish the fundamentals of a new technological platform for the realization of topological quantum computers, based on the properties of 2D-oxides. The research in this field is still at fundamental level (TRL1), thus the project activities and related identified deliverables have, as a realistic goal, the demonstration of proof of concept Topological superconductivity in 2D-oxides, and the realization of TRL3 prototype quantum gates. For these reasons, the exploitation of the project result within the three years of the project will concern mainly advancements in Research and technological innovation in quantum technologies, rather than direct industrial commercialization. In this perspective, the partners of the project will develop novel methods to study topological superconductivity, which can be eventually extended to other material and technological platforms, and novel methods to manipulate non-abelian anyons which will be of general interest for the quantum community. The list of exploitable results will be continuously updated and integrated in the present document within the project.